

GENETIC EVALUATION OF LOCAL GENOTYPES OF OKRA [*ABELMOSCHUS ESCULENTUS* (L.) MOENCH] UNDER LOW HILL CONDITIONS OF HIMACHAL PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was undertaken during Kharif season of 2018 to evaluate twenty genotypes of okra including two checks in random block design with three replications at the Experiment Farm, Department of Vegetable Science, College of Horticulture and Forestry, Neri, Hamirpur (H.P.). The analysis of variance showed significant differences ($p < 0.01$) among the twenty genotypes for all quantitative traits measured. Variability parameters indicated high PCV and GCV values for internodal length followed by fruit weight and fruit yield per plant indicating great scope for selection of these traits. While the lowest PCV and GCV values were observed for days to 50% flowering and 100 seed weight indicates the negligible influence of environment on these traits. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percentage of mean were recorded for plant height followed by first fruiting node, inter nodal length. Fruit weight, 100 seed weight and number of seeds per fruit had maximum significant positive correlation with fruit yield per plant. Fruit diameter had the highest positive direct effect on fruit yield per plant followed by hundred seed weight and fruit weight. Therefore, main emphasis should be given on these characters, while making selection in okra genotypes.

Keywords: Correlation, Genetic Advance, Genetic Variability, Heritability Abbreviations: GCV: Genotypic Coefficient Of Variation, PCV: Phenotypic Coefficient Of Heritability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench] also known as bhindi, lady's finger and ochro, is one of the widely grown vegetable in subtropical as well as tropical regions of the world. The crop is said to be the native of Ethiopia but according to recent reports, it is considered of African or Asiatic origin [22]. It belongs to the class dicotyledonae, order Malvales, family Malvaceae and genus *Abelmoschus* (syn. *Hibiscus*) having chromosome number $2n=130$. Okra has captured a prominent position among all the vegetables as it is not strictly season-bound and available almost throughout the year. The tender green mucilaginous fruits of okra are a good source of vitamins, proteins, carbohydrates, minerals, iron and iodine. 100 gm of edible pods contains 88 % of moisture, Vitamin A (88 IU), Vitamin B (63 IU) and Vitamin C (13 mg), 3100 calorie energies, 1.8g protein, 90 mg calcium and 1.0 mg iron. The fruits of okra have good medicinal value with its antispasmodic, demulcent, diaphoretic, diuretic, emollient, stimulant and vulnerary properties. The main barriers in the reduction of productivity and yield of okra includes lack of location specific varieties, pests and diseases tolerant varieties such as for fruit and shoot borer and yellow vein mosaic virus disease. Hence, the first step in okra improvement should involve evaluation of the genotype to assess the existing genetic variability for yield and yield related traits. The knowledge on nature and magnitude of variation existing in available breeding materials would help in choosing traits for effective selection of potential parents for further use in crop improvement programme.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was laid out at the Experimental Farm of Department of Vegetable Science, College of Horticulture and Forestry, Neri, Hamirpur (H.P.) India during the kharif season (June 2018) to study the genetic

variability and yield potential of twenty okra genotypes in a randomized block design (RBD) with three replications at spacing of 60x20 cm. It is located at an altitude of about 650 m above mean sea level, lying between 31°41'47.6" N latitude and 72°28'6.3" E longitude under low hill zones of Himachal Pradesh, India. The genotypes were evaluated based on their variation among twelve agro-morphological traits viz., plant height (cm) [PH], days to 50% flowering [DFF], internodal length (cm) [IL], first fruiting node [FFN], fruit length (cm) [FL], fruit diameter (cm) [FD], fresh fruit weight (g) [FW], number of fruits per plant [NFP], number of locules per fruit [NOL], number of seeds per fruit [NSF], 100 seed weight (g) [HSW] and fruit yield per plant (g) [FYP]. The data collected on different quantitative traits were processed for the analysis of variance to determine the presence of statistically significant differences between genotypes for the traits under study. Genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) and phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was estimated as per the formula given by [3]. Heritability is calculated as per formula given by [8] while the expected genetic advance resulting from selection of five percent superior individuals was calculated as per [9]. The phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of correlation were computed following [2]. Path coefficient analysis was carried out as per formula given by [5].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out for twelve traits and showed highly positive and significant differences amongst all the genotypes for these traits (Table 2). The presence of highly significant differences among all traits under study depicts the existence of large variability among genotypes. Highly positive and significant results were recorded for plant height and fruit yield per plant. The findings of [12] are similar to that of the present findings.

Genetic variability parameters (Fig. 1, Fig. 2, Fig. 3, Table 3) studies revealed that phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) values were higher than genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) values for all the characters indicating close relation between them which means environmental influence is very low and hence phenotypic performance of traits can be used a method for selection. High PCV and GCV values were observed for inter nodal length (38.77% and 36.11%), fruit weight (28.88% and 28.58%) and fruit yield per plant (25.33% and 25.31%), number of seeds per fruit (20.42% and 20.27%) whereas it was lowest for days to 50% flowering (8.93% and 8.44%) and 100 seed weight (9.64% and 9.98%) which indicated the presence of high magnitude of genetic variability in the genotypes. The similar results are reported by [13] for fruit yield per plant, [10] for fruit yield per plant and [1] for fruit yield per plant, and all ten characters displayed high heritability as well as high genetic advance as percent over mean. Crop improvement by selecting these traits would be of benefit as they show pre-dominance of additive gene effects. The results were in consolance with the findings of [6].

Genotypic Correlation Coefficient Analysis:

The estimates of phenotypic and genotypic correlation coefficients for different quantitative characters in twenty okra genotypes are depicted in Table 4 . These findings agreed [14]. The phenotypic correlation coefficients among different traits showed that fruit yield per plant had positive and significant association with fruit weight (0.95), 100 seed weight (0.94), number of seeds per fruit (0.83), fruit length (0.72), fruit diameter (0.66) and number of fruits per plant (0.48), These findings were in the consolance with the findings of [11] for number of fruits per plant; [7] for fruit diameter; [15] for number of fruits per plant and fruit diameter, whereas significant and negative correlation with days to fifty percent flowering (-0.93), first fruiting node (-0.75), plant height (-0.48) and inter nodal length (-0.11). Similarly results obtained by [14].

The genotypic correlation coefficients among different traits showed that fruit yield per plant had positive and significant association with fruit weight (0.97), 100 seed weight (0.96), number of seeds per fruit (0.85), fruit length (0.75), fruit diameter (0.74) and number of fruits per plant (0.51), whereas significant and negative correlation with days to fifty percent flowering (-0.94), first fruiting node (-0.76), plant height (-0.49) and internodal length (-0.11). The highly significant and positive association of traits are same as phenotypically except for fruit diameter which showed positive and significant correlation (0.31) with number of locules genotypically. [11] reported the similar results.

Path Coefficient Analysis:

The data revealed that the maximum positive direct effect on fruit yield per plant was exhibited by fruit diameter (0.27) followed by 100 seed weight (0.24), fruit weight (0.23), first fruiting node (0.21), fruit length

(0.18), number of fruits per plant (0.04) and internodal length (0.03) whereas maximum negative direct effect was reported by number of seeds per fruit (-0.04) followed by number of locules per fruit (-0.05), plant height (-0.05) and days to fifty percent flowering (-0.38) [4] recorded the same. Hence, it provides a basis for the selection of phenotypically superior genotypes from the diverse breeding populations.

FIGURES

Fig.1. Graphical presentation of genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation

Fig.2. Graphical presentation of heritability in broad sense (%)

Fig.3. Graphical presentation of genetic advance as percentage of mean (%)

TABLES

Table 1: List of genotypes of okra used for evaluation.

Sr. No.	Genotypes	Sr. No.	Genotypes
1.	LC-1-18	11.	LC-11-18
2.	LC-2-18	12.	LC-12-18
3.	LC-3-18	13.	LC-13-18
4.	LC-4-18	14.	LC-14-18

5.	LC-5-18	15.	LC-15-18
6.	LC-6-18	16.	LC-16-18
7.	LC-7-18	17.	LC-17-18
8.	LC-8-18	18.	LC-18-18
9.	LC-9-18	19.	Palam Komal
10.	LC-10-18	20.	P-8

Table 2: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for various characters of okra genotypes.

	Replication	Genotype	Error
df	2	14	28
Plant Height (cm)	8.86	236.50**	1.93
Fruit Girth (cm)	0.00	0.32*	0.00
Days to 50% Flowering	2.62	168.93**	1.20
Number of Fruits per Plant	0.07	64.83**	0.11
Fruit Length (cm)	0.02	23.21**	0.04
Days to 80% Maturity	5.49	657.95**	8.15
Number of Seed per Fruit	0.28	124.98**	0.521
100 Seed Weight (g)	0.04	23.19**	0.039
First Flowering Node	0.02	17.45**	0.087
Yield per Plant (g)	12.85	12369.51**	10.59

*,** Significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively

Table 3: Estimates of variability parameters for various characters of okra genotypes.

Characters	Mean	Range		Coefficient of variation (%)		Heritability (h^2)	Genetic Advance (GA)	GA as % of mean
		Min.	Max.	Phenotypic	Genotypic			
Plant height (cm)	145.16	97.65	179.60	18.06	17.99	99.35	53.64	36.95
Days to 50% flowering	44.89	40.08	53.23	08.93	8.44	89.44	7.38	16.45
First fruiting node	4.71	3.41	5.96	12.87	12.22	90.11	1.13	23.89
Internodal length (cm)	13.74	6.19	24.43	38.77	36.11	86.69	9.51	69.23
Fruit length (cm)	18.81	12.27	22.71	15.40	15.08	95.87	5.72	30.42
Fruit diameter (cm)	1.66	1.25	2.31	17.85	16.06	80.93	0.49	29.77
Fruit weight (g)	33.45	15.54	46.57	28.88	28.58	97.90	19.48	58.25
Number of locules per fruit	5.59	5.00	7.63	16.98	16.10	90.87	1.76	31.45
Number of fruits per plant	9.59	7.13	14.09	17.66	17.01	92.46	3.24	33.75
Number of seeds	61.66	36.52	78.84	20.42	20.27	98.45	25.54	41.42

per fruit												
100 seed weight (g)	6.37	5.27	7.46	09.64	9.57	98.57	1.25	19.57				
Fruit yield per plant (g)	290.01	159.86	384.59	25.33	25.31	99.89	151.14	52.12				

Table 4: Genotypic correlation coefficient studies in okra genotypes

CH	DFE	PH	FFN	IL	FL	FD	FW	NOL	NFP	NSF	HSW	FYP
DFE	1.00	0.51**	0.81**	0.19	-0.75**	-0.74**	-0.96**	-0.23	-0.51**	-0.85**	-0.94**	-0.99**
PH		1.00	0.47**	0.49**	-0.43**	-0.42**	-0.41**	-0.26*	0.09	-0.34**	-0.39**	-0.49**
FFN			1.00	0.28*	-0.69**	-0.79**	-0.79**	-0.15	-0.52**	-0.73**	-0.73**	-0.79**
IL				1.00	-0.11	-0.22	-0.15	-0.13	0.02	-0.11	-0.01	-0.12
FL					1.00	0.25	0.72**	0.02	0.53**	0.63**	0.73**	0.75**
FD						1.00	0.73**	0.11	0.21	0.69**	0.65**	0.74**
FW							1.00	0.19	0.43**	0.88**	0.94**	0.97**
NOL								1.00	-0.11	0.29*	0.29*	0.15
NFP									1.00	0.35**	0.51**	0.49**
NSF										1.00	0.84**	0.85**
HSW											1.00	0.96**

Significant at 5% level=**, Significant at 1% level =*

Table 5: Genotypic path coefficient analysis for various okra genotypes.

CH	DFE	PH	FFN	IL	FL	FD	FW	NOL	NFP	NSF	HSW	Correlation of FYP
DFE	-0.38	-0.03	0.17	0.01	-0.14	-0.20	-0.22	0.01	-0.02	0.04	-0.22	-0.99**
PH	-0.19	-0.06	0.10	0.01	-0.08	-0.11	-0.09	0.01	0.00	0.01	-0.09	-0.49**
FFN	-0.31	-0.02	0.21	0.00	-0.12	-0.21	-0.18	0.00	-0.02	0.03	-0.17	-0.79**
IL	-0.08	-0.03	0.06	0.03	-0.02	-0.05	-0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.00	-0.12
FL	0.29	0.02	-0.15	-0.00	0.18	0.07	0.16	-0.00	0.02	-0.02	0.17	0.75**
FD	0.28	0.02	-0.17	-0.00	0.05	0.27	0.17	-0.00	0.01	-0.03	0.15	0.74**
FW	0.37	0.02	-0.17	-0.00	0.13	0.19	0.23	-0.01	0.02	-0.04	0.22	0.97**
NOL	0.09	0.01	-0.03	-0.00	0.00	0.03	0.04	-0.05	-0.00	-0.01	0.07	0.15
NFP	0.19	-0.00	-0.10	0.00	0.09	0.06	0.09	0.00	0.04	-0.01	0.12	0.49**
NSF	0.32	0.02	-0.15	-0.00	0.11	0.19	0.20	-0.01	0.01	-0.04	0.20	0.84**
HSW	0.36	0.02	-0.16	-0.00	0.13	0.18	0.21	-0.02	0.02	-0.04	0.24	0.96**

Residual effect = 0.00273

IV. CONCLUSION

Genetic variability parameters (Fig. 1, Fig. 2, Fig. 3, Table 3) studies revealed that phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) values were higher than genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) values for all the characters indicating close relation between them which means environmental influence is very low and hence phenotypic performance of traits can be used a method for selection. High PCV and GCV values were observed for inter nodal length (38.77% and 36.11%), fruit weight (28.88% and 28.58%) and fruit yield per plant (25.33% and 25.31%), number of seeds per fruit (20.42% and 20.27%) whereas it was lowest for days to 50% flowering

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